

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVOLUTION OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES BY *IN SITU* HIGH ENERGY X-RAY DIFFRACTION

G. Geandier^{1,2*}, M. Salib^{1,2}, M. Mourot¹, L. Vautrot^{1,2}, M. Dehmas^{1,2}, B. Denand^{1,2},
E. Aeby-Gautier^{1,2}, S. Denis^{1,2}

¹ Institut Jean Lamour - UMR CNRS 7198 – Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France

² LabEx DAMAS – Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France

• Corresponding author (guillaume.geandier@univ-lorraine.fr)

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1 Introduction

Composite materials developed since 1970's [1] present interesting mechanical properties. Their development in the last decade is the results of the introduction of micro/nano particles in a metallic matrix. The metal provides the toughness and the particles are adding elastic stiffness, strength, hardness and wear resistance. High specific stiffness and high specific strength are interesting characteristics of Metal Matrix Composites (MMC). These features make it possible to substantially lower the weight and retain high properties. The particles must be carefully chosen for each kind of matrix and are conditioned by a thermodynamic equilibrium between the matrix and the reinforcement [2]. In order to optimize the properties of MMC by thermal treatments, it is necessary to analyze the interactions between the particles and the matrix and their role on the final microstructure [3]. The evolutions of the matrix and of the reinforcement were thus analyzed during thermal treatment using *in situ* high energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD).

In the present contribution, we analyze and compare the structural evolution of two metal matrix composites with two kinds of matrix: steel and titanium alloys both reinforced with TiC particles.

2 Experimental set-up

2.1 High energy X-ray diffraction

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) experiments were performed at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF, Grenoble, France), on the ID15B beam line. The *in situ* measurements were conducted using high energy X-ray synchrotron radiation diffraction with a monochromatic beam of 87 keV.

The high energy beam allowed to analyze a large volume of the sample, to be representative of the bulk behavior and to lessen the surface effect [4, 5]. High energy X-ray diffraction is largely used to determine the mechanical behavior of heavy samples [6]. The combination between the high flux from synchrotron source, a large area detector and the high energy allows to make *in situ* analysis of phenomena with a time scale of one second or less. The large flux of the source permits to record in a small time a high-quality diffraction signal. The large area detector allows to record the whole Debye-Scherrer diffraction rings. The use of the whole rings permits to lessen the effect of texture in the materials in the case of quantitative phase analysis [7, 5] or to analyze the texture effect [8] and extract the strain and stress evolutions in a single image [9, 10, 11].

For our experiments, the samples had a thickness of 3 mm in the beam direction. The beam size was fixed to 0.4x0.4mm². Each sample was heated using a radiant furnace allowing to heat up to 1000°C. A thermocouple was spot-welded on the sample surface leading to the measurement of temperature and allowing the control of the heating conditions. XRD patterns were recorded by a flat CCD detector (pixium 4700), with one image every 3.5s (1s exposure + 2.5s readout time). Data have been corrected and reduced to (2 θ , intensity) patterns using fit2d software [12] suitable for Rietveld analysis [13, 14]. Using the phase selectivity of the X-ray diffraction we are able to extract parameters for each phase present in the composite and due to the beam quality of the synchrotron source, phase with low fraction can be detected. The fraction limit for this technique is around 0.5%.

2.2 Samples

Mecachrome has elaborated the composites. Ti64-TiC composite contains 10vol% of TiC and steel-TiC contains 15mass% of TiC.

Matrix compositions of the composites are reported in table 1 for Ti64-TiC composite and table 2 for steel-TiC composite.

Ti	Al	V	C	Fe	O	N	H
Bal.	6.09	4	0.02	0.17	0.16	0.01	0.003

Tab.1: Composition of the matrix of Ti64-TiC composite (in mass%).

Fe	C	Cr	Mo	Mn	Si	Ni	V	N ppm
Bal.	0.31	3.83	0.72	0.43	0.59	0.07	0.12	152

Tab.2: Composition of the matrix of the steel-TiC composite (in mass%).

At first, a mechanical milling of TiC particles and matrix powders was performed at relatively low energy in order to reduce the size of both components. The consolidation of the composite powders was further realized by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) under a stress of 100 MPa at 920°C for Ti64 matrix and 1120°C for steel matrix during 4 hours.

The micrographs obtained at room temperature after HIP, are given Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

The micrographs obtained for Ti64-TiC composite (Fig 1) are given at two magnifications. At the micrometer scale, the distribution of the phases/components presents some heterogeneity with dark/grey and light areas. The dark/grey areas are related to the presence of TiC particles, while the light areas correspond to a lower concentration or the absence of reinforcement. From SEM image obtained at higher magnification (bottom) we distinguish the reinforcement in black and the two phases present in the matrix (alpha in grey and beta in white).

The steel/TiC composite presents also a non-homogeneous distribution of all components with the black components being the TiC particles, the grey area being a mixture of TiC particles and steel and the lighter area some steel powders without reinforcement [3].

Fig.1. Micrographs of the titanium matrix composite obtained by OM (top), and by SEM (BSE) (bottom).

Fig. 2. microstructure of the steel matrix composite.

3 Results

3.1 Titanium matrix composite

3.1.1 Kinetics of phase transformation

An example of the evolution of phase fraction is given for Ti-64 matrix composite (Fig. 3). In the initial state (after HIP), a mixture of three phases is characterized, consisting of 83% of α phase, 5.5% of

β and 11.5% of TiC. Phase transformations start at 600°C. Between 600°C and 720°C, the kinetics of phase transformation α to β is very slow. In this gap of temperature, the amount of TiC increases, reaching a maximum of 12.5% at 720°C. This increase of 1% is significant for the experimental technique used.

Between 720°C and 920°C (dwell temperature), the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformations kinetics is accelerated. At the end of the heating, the three phases are still present with 56 % α phase, 32 % β phase and 12 % TiC.

During the well, we can observe some oscillations that are due to the non-perfect temperature control. The amount of α phase is slightly decreasing to reach a value 51% at the end of dwell. These amounts are different from the ones expected in a Ti64 alloy. Indeed, in a Ti64 alloy, the amount of phases present at 920°C would be 46vol% of α and 54vol% of β [15]. These values are significantly different from the ones measured. Therefore the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation domain in the Ti64/TiC composite is clearly shifted toward higher temperatures.

Fig.3. mass fraction evolution during heat thermal for Ti-64/TiC composite.

During the cooling stage, the amount of α increases very quickly until 680°C and more slowly between 680°C and 550°C. At temperatures lower than 550 °C, the volume fraction of each phase remain nearly constant whereas TiC amount slightly decreases throughout the cooling. At the end of the heat treatment, the phase ratio are nearly similar to those present in the initial state. However, the rate of TiC phase increased by about 1% vol. From Ti-C phase diagram and for a given composition, small changes in TiC amount can be expected when temperature

varies [16]. Indeed, TiC as well as α and β are non stoichiometric. Moreover, TiC can be enriched in oxygen [17]

3.1.2 Cell parameters evolution

Rietveld method allowed to determine the cell parameters for each phase and their evolution during the thermal treatment. The relative cell parameter variations (see equation 1).

$$\left(\frac{a^i - a_0^i}{a_0^i} \right) \quad (1)$$

where a^i is the cell parameter of phase i for the given image number and a_0^i the cell parameter of phase i in the initial state (time 0) for Ti-64/TiC composite are also presented Fig. 4. For TiC, the relative cell parameter evolution is nearly linear during heating as well as during cooling. On the contrary large changes in the slope are observed for the relative cell parameters of the matrix.

Fig.4. Cell parameters relative evolution during heat thermal for Ti-64/TiC composite.

The relative cell parameters of the each phase of the matrix vary linearly between 20°C and 600°C. For the α phase and temperatures higher than 630°C,

both relative cell parameters (a and c) increase, but non-linearly. For da^α/a^α_0 the slope increases slightly until 920°C, while dc^α/c^α_0 present higher slope variations at temperatures > 505°C. During cooling, da^α/a^α_0 and dc^α/c^α_0 are similar to those observed during heating. For the β phase, da^β/a^β_0 increases linearly up to 550 °C. Between 550°C and 920°C da^β/a^β_0 increases abruptly reaching a value more than twice the value obtained between 20°C-500°C. This strong variation is mainly associated with the partial $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ phase transformation and the associated change in chemical composition of β [18]. On cooling the behavior is symmetrical (strong decrease of da^β/a^β_0 namely during the increase of α amounts. These behaviors for α and β phases are similar to the ones obtained for titanium alloys [18, 19]. The thermal expansion coefficient of each phase was estimated in the linear part of the evolution. Results are reported in table 3.

Phase	α ($10^{-6}K^{-1}$)	Temperature range (°C)
heating		
Ti64- α / a	10.8	30-630
Ti64- α / c	11.3	30-505
Ti64- β	10.9	30-550
TiC	8.9	30-680
cooling		
Ti64- α / a	10.7	40-660
Ti64- α / c	10.5	40-500
Ti64- β	11.3	40-450
TiC	8.2	40-895

Tab.3. experimental coefficient of thermal expansion for Ti-64/TiC composite during heating and cooling.

3.2 Steel matrix composite

For the steel-TiC composite we mainly focus on the phase transformations occurring during cooling. At the end of the heating and dwell at 1000°C, the steel-TiC composite is composed of two phases:

austenite (81.6%) and TiC (18.4%). The behavior of the phases is analyzed for two cooling conditions from 1000°C to room temperature; Condition A, slow cooling at 0.5°C/s leading to the formation of ferrite and pearlite in the metallic matrix, Condition B, cooling at 5°C/s, leading mainly to the formation of martensite in the metallic matrix.

3.2.1 Kinetics of phase transformation

The mass fraction evolutions of each phase versus temperature are given figures 5 and 6 for cooling at 0.5°C/s (condition A) and 5°C/s (condition B) respectively.

Fig.5. mass fraction evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 0.5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

Fig.6. mass fraction evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

For both cooling conditions, only austenite (γ) and TiC are present at the beginning of cooling. For condition A, a very slight increase in the mass fraction of TiC is observed until 780°C while γ amount decreases. Ferrite (α) appears at 780°C and the formation of pearlite ($\alpha + Fe_3C$) occurs between 690°C and 670°C. In that last temperature range, the TiC amount slightly increases. The change in TiC

amounts is due to differences in carbon solubility in austenite and ferrite and non-stoichiometry of the TiC phase. For that cooling rate, the transformation of the matrix leads to a mixture of ferrite and pearlite. At temperatures lower than 670°C, the amount of all phases remains constant until room temperature.

For condition B, ferrite (α) appears also at 780°C. The amount of this BCC structure increases slightly until 200°C (5 mass % at 200°C). At temperatures lower than 200°C, the martensite (tetragonal structure) is formed. The TiC amount remains stable during cooling. As martensite and ferrite have nearly the same crystallographic structure, it is not possible to distinguish the ferrite from martensite at low temperature. We have assumed that ferrite remains constant when the martensite transformation begins. For condition B, the transformation of the matrix leads to a mixture of austenite, ferrite and martensite.

3.2.2 Cell parameters evolution

The cell parameters evolutions during cooling for the steel/TiC composite are given Fig. 7, Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

Fig. 7. Cell parameters evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 0.5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

For condition A, (Fig. 7), the cell parameters evolution is linear between 1000°C and 700°C, when no phase transformation occurs or at the very early stages of the matrix transformation. During the pearlite formation (690°C-670°C), the austenite

parameter decreases while the ferrite parameter increases. The TiC cell parameter presents also an increase during this step of the matrix phase transformation. During the further cooling, we clearly evidence a non-linearity of the cells parameters of ferrite and TiC at temperatures lower than 300°C.

The CTE of the present phase was estimated in different temperature ranges. Results are reported in table 4.

Phase	α ($10^{-6}K^{-1}$)	Temperature range (°C)
austenite	22.1	750-900
ferrite	14.7	300-600
ferrite	12.2	100-300
TiC	10.7	720-900
TiC	10.4	300-600
TiC	9.1	100-300

Tab. 4: experimental coefficient of thermal expansion for steel-TiC composite during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 0.5°C/s).

These values clearly highlight the changes in the apparent CTE. Indeed, the CTE value of TiC is larger than the one measured in the Ti64-TiC composite ($8.6 \cdot 10^{-6}K^{-1}$), and generally reported in the literature [20]. It decreases significantly as temperature decreases. For condition B, from the beginning of cooling and until the martensite formation, the cell parameters of each phase decrease continuously with slight changes in the slope.

During the martensite formation, as austenite content reaches 28%, its cell parameter decreases and deviates significantly from linearity; meanwhile the TiC cell parameter increases also deviates from linearity and even increases. This is also highlighted in Fig. 9 giving in addition the cell parameters of martensite, for the temperature range 20°C- 300°C. The TiC cell parameter seems to be stagnant between 200°C and 150°C, and further increases until 50°C.

For the cell parameters of martensite, an increase of a and c is observed between 180°C and 170°C. As temperature is further decreased and martensite amount increases, a parameter decreases while c parameter increases.

Fig.8. Cell parameters evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

Fig.9. Cell parameters evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite in the low temperature range

Phase	α ($10^{-6}K^{-1}$)	Temperature range (°C)
austenite	20.4	300-500
ferrite	15.1	300-500
TiC	10.9	300-500

Tab.5. experimental coefficient of thermal expansion for steel-TiC composite during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s).

For the martensite, both parameters goes to tension at the beginning of the transformation, its means an increases of the cell volume. In the same time TiC parameters seems to be stagnant. With cooling down and transformation advancement, c parameters increases and a decreases. In the same time, TiC parameters goes in tension. The thermal expansion coefficient of the present phase was estimated in the linear part of the evolution, results are reported in table 5.

4 full width at half maximum

In addition to the mean cell parameter variation we have also characterized the mean full width at half maximum (fwhm) evolution for each phase during the heat treatments. Such parameter can also give important information. From Rietveld refinement, we can extract parameters u, v and w that can be further used to calculate the fwhm using the Caglioti formula:

$$fwhm = U \tan^2\theta + V \tan\theta + W \quad [21]$$

We have calculated the fwhm during each cooling for our composites and we have reported the results on Fig. 10, 11, 12 respectively for Ti-64/TiC composite, steel/TiC composite with condition A, and steel/TiC composite with condition B.

4.1 fwhm of titanium matrix composite

Fwhm evolution during cooling for all phases are presented in figure 10.

Fig.10. FWHM evolution during cooling (920°C to 20°C at 15°C/min) for Ti-64/TiC composite.

For TiC and α phase, the fwhm values are low at the beginning of cooling (0.030° for α and 0.038° for TiC). These values are decreasing during the whole cooling, more quickly between 920°C and 600°C while α amount increases. For β phase, the fwhm is of the same order of magnitude as the other phases at the beginning of cooling (0.035°). However, the value increases very significantly during cooling; a first increase (up to 0.06°) is observed between 920°C and 600°C , while α amount increases, and a second strong increase (up to 0.11°) is observed between 600°C and 420°C . For temperatures lower than 400°C , the fwhm for β is slightly decreasing.

4.2 fwhm of steel matrix composite

The fwhm evolution during cooling are plotted versus temperature in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, for condition A and condition B respectively.

Fig.11. FWHM evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 0.5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

At the beginning of cooling, the fwhm values are low both for austenite (0.020°) and TiC (0.030°). For condition A, a slight decrease of fwhm is observed between 1000°C and 850°C followed by an increase of fwhm until the beginning of ferrite formation. During the ferrite/pearlite formation fwhm of TiC and γ is decreasing, even quite abruptly for γ . As α phase is formed, the associated fwhm values are quite high at the early stages of the transformation (0.09° to 0.10°) and they decrease reaching a value lower than 0.02° at 650°C . This value remains constant until room temperature. Meanwhile, fwhm of Fe_3C remains constant and the

one of TiC continuously increases. , for TiC we can note an increase of the fwhm meaning some stress gradient in TiC particles. Fwhm data between 690°C and 670°C are difficult to interpret due the difficulties to fit the XRD diagrams during Rietveld analysis due to the small amount of phase present, the complexity of the cementite phase that conduct to low intensity peaks.

Fig.12. FWHM evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite.

Fig.13. FWHM evolution during cooling (1000°C to 20°C at 5°C/s) for steel/TiC composite as a function of martensite mass fraction (200°C to 20°C).

For condition B, TiC and austenite fwhm have a similar behavior as for condition A between 1000°C and 780°C . At this temperature, where ferrite appears, we can notice a very small decrease of the fwhm of TiC and austenite and then the both phases'

fwhm increases until the formation of martensite. In the same time, we notice high values of the fwhm of ferrite that are decreasing (from 0.14° to 0.10°). At temperatures lower than 200°C , when martensite is forming, fwhm of TiC is still increasing up to values of 0.044° . The fwhm value of austenite is increasing up to 0.06° while for martensite, fwhm is firstly decreasing and further increases when temperature is below 130°C . The final value of fwhm of martensite remains high (0.09).

5 Discussion

Thanks to the high energy X-ray diffraction we were able to characterize the evolution of the phases in the different CMM as well as their mean cell parameter and fwhm. As heat treatments were performed in temperature ranges where phase transformations (at least in the matrix) occur, we were able to characterize the effect of the reinforcement on the phase transformation kinetics in the matrix.

Indeed, for Ti-64/TiC composite, we obtain after dwell at 920°C a mixture of TiC, α and β phases. α and β amounts in the matrix are far from the ones expected in a Ti-64 alloy at the same temperature. This means that the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation domain is shifted to higher temperatures. This shift can be associated with changes in the matrix composition. If some modification in carbon and titanium amounts can be expected, the effect of carbon on the equilibrium α phase amount and equilibrium temperature is low. For Ti-C phase diagram, the temperature at which no more α is present is increased by 40°C [16]. We performed additional experiments and determined the limit temperature of the two phases domain (β +TiC). The value obtained is near 1200°C . Different authors also reported such result. They attributed the increase in the limit temperature to an increase in the oxygen amount introduced during the milling process. This higher oxygen amount will strongly increase the beta transus temperature of the titanium matrix, and in consequence increase the α amount at a given temperature.

In the case of the steel/TiC composite, we have shown that the presence of reinforcement favors the transformation at the higher temperatures as compared to a steel specimen without TiC [3]. We

mainly focus on the cell parameter evolution.

The cell parameter evolution that were characterized during the heat treatments may be due to 3 factors: variation of temperature, variation of chemical composition of the phase, variation in the mean elastic strain in the phase. Analyzing simultaneously the fwhm variations, those ones are associated with heterogeneities in temperature, in chemical composition and in elastic strains.

For Ti64-TiC composite, the applied heat treatment leads to a diffusive phase transformation of the matrix. In addition, some chemical reaction may occur between the matrix and the reinforcement.

For steel/TiC composite, some changes in the composition of the phases (austenite for example) may occur at the lower cooling rate (condition A), as well as some chemical reaction between the matrix and the reinforcement. However for the higher cooling rate, for which a martensitic transformation is mainly occurring, the chemical reaction between TiC particles and the matrix should be low and the martensite formation is considered as a transformation without diffusion.

We have reported in Table 3 the CTE of the different phases. For the Ti64-TiC, the CTE values obtained for α and β phases are near the ones reported in the literature [22]. For TiC the values obtained are larger than the ones given in the literature $8.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [20]

The CTE of α and β present a non-linear behavior at temperatures higher than 550°C . Moreover, the apparent CTE of β phase is largely increased during the $\alpha \leftrightarrow \beta$ transformation. The large increase in apparent β CTE was observed in different Ti alloys. Isothermal characterization of phase transformation allowed to associate this behavior with the change in composition of the beta phase during the phase transformation [18]. In addition, changes in the fwhm were mentioned too associated with heterogeneities in the β phase composition during the transformation. For the higher transformation temperatures, fwhm increased and further decreased as transformation was completed. At the lower transformation temperatures, fwhm increases nearly continuously, and did not decrease. This behavior was associated with a dispersed stress state due to the

transformation strain [19]. For our experiments, fwhm increases during the transformation: a first increase is observed between 920°C and 600°C and a second one, larger in amplitude between 600°C and 400°C. For the first increase, the change in transformation amounts is large. The fwhm can mainly be associated with heterogeneities in composition in beta. At the lower temperatures, the amount of α formed is low (0.6% between 400°C and 20°C). The increase in fwhm can be due to stresses, either to thermal stresses or to transformation stresses. As fwhm decreases at temperatures lower than 400°C, these stresses are mainly transformation stresses.

Analyzing the cell parameters evolution versus temperature for the steel/TiC composite, two major features can be pointed out: i) significant variations of cell parameters during the transformations ii) deviations from a linear behavior during the cooling.

The apparent CTE obtained in table 4 and 5 led to different values. We first point out the apparent CTE of TiC. The values characterized are near $10.7\text{-}10.9\cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$ in the high temperature range. These values are larger than the value obtained for the Ti64-TiC composite, and about 30% larger than those reported in the literature. Such difference cannot be associated with a change in the chemical composition of the TiC during cooling. It is due to thermal stresses in the composite. As austenite CTE is nearly 3 times larger than that of TiC, stresses are generated in both phases. The apparent CTE of TiC increases while that of austenite decreases. TiC reinforcements have a mean compression state, while the austenite grains have a mean tensile strain. After transformation, when the matrix is mainly composed of pearlite (CTE near $12\cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$) the apparent CTE of TiC is lower ($9\cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$).

In addition to the thermal stresses, these results highlight the role of the transformation strain on changes in the local stress states. For both conditions, the transformation occurs with an increase in the atomic volume. This change leads to an increase of the TiC cell parameter during the pearlite formation as well as during the martensite formation. If we consider that the CTE of TiC particles is near $8\cdot 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$, the TiC particles are in a mean compression state before the transformation. The volume increase associated with the

transformation will lower the mean compression. On the other hand, the austenite was in a mean tensile state, and the transformation will lead to decrease this mean tensile state. The increase in fwhm is again associated with a spread of the local elastic strains due to the spatial distribution of the phases and some possible local plasticity (dislocation density) [23].

Additional analysis of these results needs a micromechanical model leading to the local strain distribution during the treatment.

6 Concluding remarks

High energy diffraction is a powerful tool to highlight the microstructure evolution during thermal treatments. Evolution of the phase fraction and cell parameters during thermal treatments of metal matrix composites (titanium and steel matrix) shown that their exist chemical exchange between the matrix and the reinforcement. These exchanges modify the phase transformation kinetics. Moreover we highlight the formation of stresses in each phase during the transformation and during thermal treatment (without phase transformation). Those stresses have to be considered regarding the final properties of the composite.

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